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A Study Of Parental Occupation In Relation To Academic Performance Of Students In Colleges Of Education

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Abstract

The main aim of this study was to explore the effect of family socio-economic status (occupation) on students' academic Achievement. Descriptive survey research design was employed. Systematic methods of review were using by sourcing both primary and secondary data particularly documentary sources. Thematic analysis used in describing the related empirical studies. Occupation is widely recognized as a critical factor influencing an individual's social and economic success, as it provides a pathway to improved opportunities and a better quality of life. Nigeria is a nation with people that are classified on the basis of socio-economic status. These classes are high, middle and low socio-economic status. This class or division has implication for the type of school a child goes to in Nigeria. Privates' high schools are restricted to special family only. It was discovered by this research that rich parents can spends more than the poor parents and that investment may lead to better outcomes for their children. It also learnt that poverty alone does not account for all the difference in the performance of the students. the paper recommends among others to encourage and involve parents from all socio-economic backgrounds in their children's education. Provide opportunities for parents to establish effective communication channels to bridge the gap between lower class and high class of parents.

Keywords: Parents, Occupation, Education, Academic achievement

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Education is widely recognized as a critical factor influencing an individual's social and economic success, as it provides a pathway to improved opportunities and a better quality of life (OECD, 2020). Academic achievement, measured by factors such as test scores, grade point averages, and educational attainment, is often considered a crucial indicator of educational success (Sirin, 2005). However, numerous studies have consistently demonstrated that socio-economic status (SES) plays a significant role in shaping academic achievement outcomes (Reardon, 2011; Sirin, 2005).

Socio-economic status refers to the social and economic position of individuals or families within a society, encompassing various dimensions such as income, parental education level, occupation, and access to resources and opportunities (readorn, 2011). SES is a multifaceted construct that reflects both material and social advantages or disadvantages (Duncan & Magnuson, 2012). It is well-established in many researches that individuals from higher socio-economic backgrounds tend to have better access to

educational resources, including quality schools, tutoring, books, and technology, which can contribute to enhanced academic performance (Reardon, 2011; Sirin, 2005; Duncan & Magnuson, 2012).

Nigeria is a nation with people that are classified on the basis of socio-economic status. These classes are high, middle and low socio-economic status. This class or division has implication for the type of school a child goes to in Nigeria. School attendance influences school performance, which may be attributed to economic and social influence of the child's family background. The main source of conflict attitude in formal western education in Nigeria today, is the cost of educational learning process at all levels. Children from high socio-economic background may stand a better chance of school attendance and good academic performance than children from low socio-economic background.

The type of family a child is born into, in no small measure determines his individuality. Parent's socio-economic status therefore, strongly affects the academic performance of their children especially in a class society where power is based on wealth and those with power wish to preserve the present advantage, they have in distribution not merely of wealth but also of knowledge and prestige. In this way they can ensure their children's future status (Musgrave, 1998). Socio-economic indices include parent's level of education, occupation, source of income, amount of income and dwelling place. All these tend to explain the nature of parents' influence on their children's schooling. According to Earmon (2005) socio-economic status and social background determine the student's ability to enrol in school. Children from high socio-economic status have better opportunity to further their education up to university level with less difficulty. Children from poor families' even with parental encouragement most of the time dropout of the educational system when their parents cannot for example pay school fees.

Earmon (2005) found that socio-economic background of a family affects the student's academic performance at all levels. Students with low socio-economic background have been found to score about ten percent lower than students with higher socio-economic background. This statement clearly showed that if the socio-economic status of a student is low, his educational accomplishment is likely to be less. Thus, student's academic achievement depends on their parent's socio-economic condition because low socio-economic conditions prevent the access of students to education resources and create additional stress and anxiety at home.

It's against this background that this research work wishes to find out how economic background of occupation is affecting their academic performance in Sokoto state with emphasis on Shehu Shagari college of education Sokoto.

Research problem

Despite the effort of the government through employment of teachers and community through construction of classrooms, laboratories and putting up new facilities in the higher institutions, the problem of transport cost has been raising especially in the present era of economic hardship of 2024/2025 session. Students from the poor financial background are finding it difficult to go to school every day from per distance. After transport cost there is the issue of feeding and learning materials which all depend on the family financial support. Another alarming issue is that all the vehicles provided to support the student transportation are down as a result of poor patronage by students. In contrary those from higher class of family are still driving vehicles, motorcycles or sponsored by parent to be in school regularly. Reconnaissance survey of this research shows that students particularly from rural areas inculcate the habits of not returning back to school after holidays till towards ends of the semester usually two weeks to examinations. Blaming the economic hardship factor to cater for their school living. This situation is very worrying among many students from the lower class of parents. The study therefore addresses the problem by finding out the effect of occupation as socio-economic factor that influence student's academic performance in Shehu Shagari College of education, Sokoto.

METHODOLOGY

The research aims to investigate the impact of occupation as part of Socio-economic status on academic achievement. A design of systematic review was employed, which is comprehensive and structured approach to identifying, evaluating and synthesizing all relevant studies on a specific research question.

Thematic analysis is used for describing the results of many researches in synthesizing the findings of the concluded studies. Both primary and secondary data will be analyses for this purpose

Significance of the Study

Sokoto state has been winning the poorest state in Nigeria for several years (NaijaDetails, 2024). And at the same time the state is one of the states that have masses failure in SSCE and NECO results in the country. The study on the influence of family socioeconomic factors on the student academic performance can be linked to above assertion. Therefore, this research can be found useful to both educational and policy makers in giving guidance to the Government on necessary course of action to enhance academic achievement of students. It may also enable the parent to understand the critical roles they play for their children to perform well in school. The finding may be useful feedback to curriculum designers into kind of experiences in secondary school needed to aid in successful academic performance. Finally, the study may help the future researchers in identifying priority areas in which government can help in assisting the less privilege in carrying out the successful student's academic performance in colleges of education.

Conceptual Framework

Socio-economic status is a composite measure that reflects an individual's or a household's relative position within a social hierarchy. It comprises several key components:

Income: The amount of money earned by individuals or households, including wages, salaries, investments, and government transfers (Adler & Rehkopf, 2008; Galobardes, Shaw, Lawlor, Lynch, & Davey Smith, 2006).

Education: The level of formal education attained by an individual, such as completing primary, secondary, or tertiary education (Gottfredson, 2004; Sirin, 2005).

Occupation: The type of work an individual engages in, often categorized by skill level, industry, and level of responsibility (Adler & Rehkopf, 2008; Gottfredson, 2004).

Wealth: The accumulation of assets, including property, investments, and savings, which provides a measure of financial stability and security (Galobardes et al., 2006).

Impact of Socio-economic Status on Individuals

Health Outcomes: Socio-economic status is strongly correlated with health outcomes. Higher SES individuals tend to have better access to healthcare, healthier lifestyles, and lower levels of stress, leading to better overall health (Adler & Rehkopf, 2008).

Education and Employment Opportunities: Individuals from higher socio-economic backgrounds often have greater access to quality education and better employment opportunities, leading to higher earning potential and career advancement (Gottfredson, 2004; Sirin, 2005).

Housing and Living Conditions: Socio-economic status influences housing options, with higher SES individuals having access to better-quality housing, safer neighborhoods, and improved living conditions (Galobardes et al., 2006).

Social Capital and Networks: Higher SES individuals tend to have access to broader social networks, which can provide additional opportunities for personal growth, career advancement, and social support (Gemechu, 2018).

Impact of Socio-economic Status on Society

Inequality and Social Mobility: Socio-economic status plays a crucial role in perpetuating or reducing inequality within societies. Lower socio-economic status often leads to limited social mobility, as individuals face barriers to accessing opportunities for upward mobility (Corak, 2013).

Crime and Social Unrest: Areas with high concentrations of individuals from lower socio-economic backgrounds may experience higher crime rates and social unrest due to limited access to resources, higher levels of poverty, and decreased opportunities for socio-economic advancement (Jeynes, 2002).

Education and Workforce Productivity: Socio-economic disparities in educational opportunities and resources can lead to a less productive workforce and hinder economic growth and innovation (Duncan et al, 2012).

Public Health and Welfare: The socio-economic status of a population impact public health outcomes and welfare expenditure. Lower SES groups may require greater public support in terms of healthcare, social assistance, and community development initiative (Mweti, 2013).

Defining Socio-economic Status

Income, education, occupation, and wealth are just some of the many factors that make up a person's Socio-economic position. It is used as an indicator of a person's or family's overall Socio-economic status (parker, 2003).

The Relationship between Socio-economic Status and Academic Achievement

There is a robust correlation between family income and academic performance, as shown by a large body of research. The educational attainment, test scores, and general academic performance of students from higher SES origins are often higher than those of those from lower SES backgrounds. The term "achievement gap" is commonly used to describe this gap in educational success. Students from wealthier Socio-economic backgrounds tend to perform better in school, as demonstrated in research conducted by Sirin (2005). Pong (2007) and Bradley and Corwyn (2002) showed similar findings, highlighting the importance of Socio-economic position on educational achievements.

Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by the systems theory of organizations developed Ludwig von Bertalanffy in the 1950s. Systems theory emerged as part of the intellectual ferment following World War II although its roots are much older.

Systems theory postulate that schools are like other open systems which of necessity engage in various mode of exchange with environment (Sirin, 2005). Systems theory emphasizes the consideration of the relationships between the school and its environment as well as what goes on within the school. The fundamental concept in the general system theory is the notion of emergence and interaction.

As adapted in this study, the systems theory holds that socioeconomic factors influences“ students’ academic performance in a school. That is parental level of education, parental involvement in children education, income of parent and financial and material support given to the children by the parent influences students’ academic performance. This theory has its own shortcomings. The interrelationships among part of a system have to be recognized and understood by „all“ people involved. The theory also requires a shared vision so that all people in the school have an idea of what they are to accomplish.

Empirical Review

Influence of Income of the Parent on student performance

Many studies have been carried out in under develop and developed countries on parent’s occupational and socio-economic influence on children’s academic achievement and have indicated its positive relationship with academic achievement. Studies carried out in the developing countries though few, reveal similar results.

The United States department of education (2000) concluded that poverty is an important Factor accounting for differences in performance and achievement across rural, sub-urban and urban districts. However, the study concluded that poverty alone does not account for all the difference in the performance of the student. Johnson, 1996 (as cited in Farooq, 2011), Opined that poverty of the parents has elastic effects on their children academic works as they lack enough resources and funds to sponsor their education and good school, good housing facilities and medical care and social welfare services.

Gordon, and Lance, (2005), observed that children growing up in poor families are likely to have home environments or face other challenges which would continue to affect development even if family income rose substantially. They also said that for children growing up in poor families, extra income does appear to have a positive causal effect.

Susan, (2010), notes that the children of affluent parents are more likely to succeed in life than the children of poor parents. For example, compared to more affluent children, poor children, score lower on tests of cognitive skill in early childhood have more behavior problems in school and at home, are more

likely to have children at a young age, and are more likely to be poor themselves when they are adults. The most initiative explanation for this difference is that rich parents can spend more than poor parents on their children and that these “investments” lead to better outcomes for their children. Susan further said that if poor children fail because their parents cannot make sufficient monetary investments in their future, then government can improve the life chances of poor children by providing families with the means to make the investments or by providing the investments directly in the form of schooling, health care and other human capital inputs. Greg. (2005), state that family income has substantial but decidedly selective associations with children’s attainments. The selective nature of effects included the following: Family income had much larger associations with measures of children’s ability and achievement than with measures of behavior, mental health and physical health. Family economic conditions in early childhood appeared to be more important for shaping ability and achievement than did economic conditions during adolescence; and the association between income and achievement appeared to be non-linear, with the biggest impacts at the lowest level of income.

The level of the family income is one of the most powerful influences on demand for secondary and higher education and even primary school enrolment rates in developing countries (Sulaiman et’al, 2012). The rise in poverty levels indicates that 46.8% of Kenyan lives below poverty line. Today more than 56% of Kenyan lives below poverty line. Income of the parent influences students’ performance because it determines the availability of education material or lack of it, and availability school fees or lack of it.

Influence of parental Financial and material support to their children’s successful learning on student academic performance

According to Teachman, 1987(as cited in Zahyah, 2008), parents use material and non-material resources to create a home atmosphere that fosters academic skills. It is through these resources allocated to children that may influence attainment of learning in children. Similarly, the availability of educational resources in the home were usually associated with homes where parents were not only educated but were also financially stable. For example, children whose parents were economically resourceful tend to associate educational materials with academic achievement. Parents see these materials as agents for promoting their children interest in learning.

Zahyah, (2008), concluded that parent socioeconomic factors are related to adolescents’ academic achievement his study was based on the rural area. He said that it is not so much of the geographical settings but more of the parents’ economic status. The educational level and reading materials in the home to a certain extent do influence children’s school performance. He further state that poor performance in school does not fully depend on location but more so on parents’ socio-economic status. The presence of reading materials in the home is found to be moderately associated with adolescents in purchasing the appropriate reading materials based on their own academic ability compared to parents with lower educational background. He was carrying out a study on the relationship between aspects of socio-economic factors and academic achievement. Parker, (2003), in his theoretical model of economic nationalism in developing states, said that poor parents can no longer provide adequately for shelter, clothing and special needs in school (such as provision of textbooks, school uniforms and good medical care). He further stated that high levels of illiteracy, poverty and low socioeconomic status coupled with high rate of paternal and maternal deprivation of students’ academic needs, which was necessitated by poor socioeconomic of the country threw many farmers and rural dwellers into untold financial problems such as poverty, lack of money to purchase necessary textbooks and working materials for their kids. This kind of poverty of the parents make it difficult for them to provide basic needs such as food, stationaries, reading tables and study rooms at home for day schooling learners.

According to Parson et al. (2001), socio-economic status is a term that differentiates the family income, political power, educational background and employment status relative to other people in the Community. Saifi and Mehmood (2011) stated that the socio-economic status of an individual or family based on income, education and occupation is a combined measure of the economic and social position. The socio-economic background has been shown to be responsible for the students’ academic success through research studies (Jeynes, 2002; Eamon, 2005). Poor socio-economic status is considered to have

major detrimental effects on students' academic success since low socio-economic status impedes exposure to very valuable opportunities and causes external pressures at home (Eamon 2005).

The weak socio-economic status of students produces bad outcomes and may cause one to quit school (Eamon, 2005). Farooq et al. (2011) examined factors which influence secondary school students' academic performance in a Pakistan's metropolitan city. The results indicated that the higher level of SES, the better measure for the standard of students' results. Suleman et al. (2012) carried out an impact study on the academic performance of high school students in Karak District, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan in 60 government high schools for boys of the 10th class. The study showed that parenting socio-economic status affects the secondary-school students' academic achievement.

CONCLUSION

Findings of the study revealed that socioeconomic background, parental involvement especially financial support are very crucial factors in determining students' achievement in high schools of Sokoto State. The paper concludes that, poverty alone does not account for all the difference in the performance of the students and that poverty of the parents has elastic effects on the children academic works as they lack enough resources and funds to sponsor their education. It was observed that children growing up in poor families are likely to have challenges of extra income. However, children of affluent parents are more likely to succeed in life than the children of poor parents. The most initiative explanation for these differences is that rich parents can spend more than the poor parents and that investments may lead to better outcomes for their children. Today more than 56% of Kenyan lives below poverty line. Income of the parents influences students' performance because it determines the availability of education material or lack of it and opportunities of paying school fees.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the basis of findings;

1. There is need of proper sensitization of families on the need and importance of supporting children's education, this may ginger the parents in indulging into many occupational opportunities.
2. Encourage and involve parents from all socio-economic backgrounds in their children's education. Provide opportunities for parents to establish effective communication channels to bridge the gap between lower level and high-class level of parents.
3. Develop targeted interventions and support programs for students from low socio-economic backgrounds. These can include additional academic support, tutoring, mentoring, and counselling services to address specific challenges they may face.
4. Focus on early identification and intervention for students at risk of falling behind academically. Implement strategies such as early literacy and numeracy programs, preschool education, and comprehensive support systems to address potential learning gaps before they become more significant.

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